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The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine has agreed the use of the uniform requirements of manuscripts submitted to biomedical journals published by the INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE OF MEDICAL JOURNAL EDITORS (ICMJE) and it's the first Iraqi peer-review medical journal listed by the ICMJE journal list. The first two issues of this journal appeared under the title of Al Karkh journal of Medicine

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The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine: More goals to achieve

Aamir Jalal Al Mosawi

The benefit of scientific medical peer-reviewed writing and publication is to document scientific facts, practices, and new hypothesis and apply proven facts to patient care by challenging the current practices and subjecting them to the judgment of peers. In this way the scientific knowledge is advanced contributing to improved patient care, medical and health practices.

There has been a tremendous need for an independent peer-reviewed medical journal which aims at the advancement of medical knowledge.

From the first beginning of this journal in 2005 as Al Karkh Journal of Medicine, the decision was made that

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the journal should adhere to the internationally accepted standards of modern peer-reviewed medical journals. Publication ethics (COPE) All the editorial policies were adapted from the policies of the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE), World Association of Medical editors (WAME), and the Committee on The first two issues of the journal which appeared under the title Al Karkh Journal of Medicine were introductory issues published reviews, editorials about the journal policies (Authorship and contributorship of medical papers, and The Role of the Editor) and a letter from the former president of the WAME Peush Sahni (WAME aims and Policies). Despite the serious difficulties in publishing a peer-reviewed medical journal here the journal has grown and from the third issue of December 2005 the journal has become The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine the official peer-reviewed medical journal of the Iraqi ministry of health.

Initially, the primary goal of the Journal was to publish research work confined to Iraq, which were of importance for both.

Bernard Ferguson, JD
President
International Association
of Medical Colleges

Aamir J Al Mosawi
Head Copernicus scientists
International panel-Iraq

Andre MEGARBANE

local and international readers. Another aim was to make the research work easily available for international readers. Thus a sincere attempt is being made to disseminate the medical knowledge to all medical fraternity of the world.

A good number of Iraqi authors have published their work in the Eastern Mediterranean health journals and Saudi medical journals. These are available for both local and international readers and researchers. However, adequate data on the practice of medicine and research in Iraq, are still not readily available.

From the September 2007 issue, there would be 5000 copies of the New Iraqi Journal of Medicine distributed for both local and international readers. This achievement wouldn't have been possible without the support of Executive Editor and Senior Deputy Minister of Health, Amir Alkhuza'ie.

The PDF version of the journal has already being distributed throughout the world. Abstracts of all previously published papers are also available at the website of the journal at: www.newiraqijm.4t.com

The web site of the journal is linked to the yahoo and Google search engines. The PDF version of all published papers is available currently for free for every one requesting them.

From September 2007 issue of the journal, various editors from all parts of the world joined our journal. Now we have editors from 4 major continents in the world: American Editor, [Craig Vanderwagen](#), European Editor, Silvio Maringhini, African Editor Adamson S. Muula, and Asian Editor, Srijit Das. Our British editor Ali Kubba is section Editor of Gynecology and obstetrics. He is also an expert in sexual disorder. In addition we have an International Editorial Board that includes Bernard Ferguson, JD, President International Association of Medical Colleges, Daniele Trevisanuto, Andre Megarbane,

SM Kadri, Anurag Tewari, Reza Gharebaghi and is also on the verge of

Das Srijit

continuous expansion. International editors including editorial board have the privileges of the Editor in Chief, as they can receive, evaluate manuscripts and provide the journal with an editorial decision.

Anurag Tewari

International Editors and International Editorial Board have already contributed to the fulfillment of the main journal goal, which is the publication of internationally peer-reviewed medical papers.

Until now the journal has been successful in publishing papers in more than 15 areas and disciplines of

medicine Figure-1. Authors located in Iraq, USA, India, Malaysia, Jordan, Malawi, and Zambia have contributed to the journal. Figure -2 shows the country distribution of authors who have contributed to the journal

Figure (1): Discipline distribution of the published papers

Figure (2): Country distribution of authors who have contributed to the journal

I wish that the growth of the New Iraqi Journal of Medicine into an International peer – reviewed medical journal represents an illuminated feature of this dark times witnessed by Iraq. I would also invite and encourage all researchers

all over the world to send their valuable contributions to New Iraqi Journal of Medicine.

Table-1 shows the journal achievements as an Iraqi medical journal.

Table (1) :The journal achievements

- 1-The first Iraqi journal to be listed by the ICMJE**
- 2-Indexation: EMR index medicus ,and Copernicus journal master list**
- 3- First Iraqi journal in publishing papers for authors from outside Iraq; USA, India, Malaysia, and Jordan, Zambia, and Malawi.**
- 4-The only Iraqi journal displayed at the exhibition of the Third Regional Conference on Medical Journals in The Eastern Mediterranean**
- 5-Committee on publication ethics membership (London)**
- 6-The only internationally peer-reviewed Iraqi medical journal**